

Existence of equations governing right triangle within the smallest acute angle of the right triangle

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Abstract

We prove that equations governing right triangle whose hypotenuse side and non-hypotenuse side (adjacent side) differ by any positive integer greater than zero within the smallest acute angle of the right triangle do exist.

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1 Introduction

In 1995 C.C. Chan and T.A. Peng proved the existence of infinitely many right triangles with integral sides in which lengths of two non-hypotenuse sides differ by 1 as shown in [2]. *But does the right triangle whose hypotenuse side and non-hypotenuse side (adjacent side) differ by any positive integer greater than zero within the smallest acute angle of the right triangle exist?* Let us call such triangle a *Mambosasa triangle*, also let the difference between hypotenuse side and non-hypotenuse side (adjacent side) be a *Mambosasa triangle order*. *But do equations governing Mambosasa triangle exist?* Answers to both questions will be shown in this paper.

2 Preliminaries

In this section we recall some definitions and basic notations of the Mambosasa triangle in **fig 1**.

Fig 1. Mambosasa Triangle (see definition 3)

Definition 1. Let b , c and m to denote non-hypotenuse side (adjacent side), hypotenuse side and Mambosasa triangle order of the right triangle respectively such that

$$m = c - b$$

if and only if

$$0 < m \leq \infty.$$

Definition 2. Minimum angle is the smallest acute angle of the right triangle such that if (θ) is an acute angle then minimum angle is

$$0^\circ < \theta \leq 45^\circ$$

within the right triangle.

Definition 3. Mambosasa triangle is the right triangle whose hypotenuse side and non-hypotenuse side (adjacent side) differ by any positive integer greater than zero within the smallest acute angle of the right triangle.

3.0 Main Results

Theorem 3.1 *If the difference between hypotenuse side and non-hypotenuse side (adjacent side) is the Mambosasa triangle order then*

$$b = c - m \tag{1}$$

Proof. In fact, it follows that definition (1) satisfies Theorem (3.1) \square

Theorem 3.2 *If θ satisfies definition (2) then the adjacent side (b) of the right triangle is*

$$\frac{m \cos \theta}{1 - \cos \theta}$$

if and only if m satisfies definition (1).

Proof. Let us first recall that $\cos \theta = \frac{\text{adjacent}}{\text{Hypotenuse}}$ as in [1, 4]

$$\cos \theta = \frac{b}{c} \tag{2}$$

We substitute equation (1) into equation (2)

$$\cos \theta = \frac{b}{b + m}$$

$$(b + m) \times \text{Cos}\theta = \frac{b}{b + m} \times (b + m)$$

$$(b + m)\text{Cos}\theta = b$$

$$b\text{Cos}\theta + m\text{Cos}\theta = b$$

$$m\text{Cos}\theta = (b - b\text{Cos}\theta)$$

$$m\text{Cos}\theta = b(1 - \text{Cos}\theta)$$

we thus get

$$b = \frac{m\text{Cos}\theta}{1 - \text{Cos}\theta} \tag{3}$$

which proves Theorem 3.2. Now we show examples in **table 1**. □

Theorem 3.3 *If B is the isosceles triangle base then*

$$B = 2(c - m)$$

if and only if m satisfies definition (1).

Fig 2. Isosceles triangle

Proof. Our proof starts with the observation that *b* is the adjacent side of the right triangle **QRS** in **fig 2**, then let

$$b + b = 2b. \tag{4}$$

Then let us substitute equation (1) into equation (4) which gives

$$2b = 2(c - m).$$

Then let

$$2b = B,$$

therefore

$$B = 2(c - m) \tag{5}$$

which completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3.4 *If hypotenuse side of the right triangle satisfies definition (1) then*

$$c = \frac{m}{1 - \cos\theta}$$

if and only if m satisfies definition (1) and θ satisfies definition (2).

Proof. Let $\cos\theta = \frac{\text{adjacent}}{\text{hypotenuse}}$ as in [1, 4]

$$\cos\theta = \frac{b}{c}$$

But

$$b = c - m \text{ (see equation 1)}$$

We thus get

$$\cos\theta = \frac{c - m}{c}$$

$$c \times \cos\theta = \frac{(c - m)}{c} \times c$$

$$c \cos\theta = c - m$$

$$c - c \cos\theta = m$$

$$c(1 - \cos\theta) = m$$

$$c = \frac{m}{1 - \cos\theta} \tag{6}$$

which completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3.5 *If h is the height of the right triangle, m is the Mambosasa triangle order and c is the hypotenuse side of the same right triangle then*

$$h^2 = 2mc - m^2$$

if and only if both h and m satisfy definition (1).

Proof. Let us first recall *Pythagoras theorem* ($h^2 + b^2 = c^2$) as in [1,3, 5]. (7)

Then we substitute equation (1) into equation (7)

we thus get

$$h^2 + (c - m)^2 = c^2$$

$$h^2 + (c - m)(c - m) = c^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 h^2 + (c^2 - cm - cm + m^2) &= c^2 \\
 h^2 + (c^2 - 2cm + m^2) &= c^2 \\
 h^2 + c^2 - 2cm + m^2 &= c^2 \\
 h^2 - 2cm + m^2 &= c^2 - c^2 \\
 h^2 - 2cm + m^2 &= 0
 \end{aligned}$$

then we obtain that

$$h^2 = 2cm - m^2 \quad (8)$$

therefore the proof is complete. \square

Theorem 3.6 *If both h and m satisfy definition (1) then*

$$h = \frac{m \sin \theta}{1 - \cos \theta}$$

if and only if θ satisfies definition (2)

Proof. Let $\sin \theta = \frac{\text{Opposite}}{\text{Adjacent}}$ as in [1, 4]

$$\sin \theta = \frac{h}{c} \quad (9)$$

then we substitute equation (6) into equation (9)

thus we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
 h &= \frac{m}{1 - \cos \theta} \times \sin \theta \\
 h &= \frac{m \sin \theta}{1 - \cos \theta}
 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

which completes the proof of theorem 3.6 \square

Theorem 3.7 *If c is the hypotenuse side of the right triangle then area of the right triangle (A) is*

$$\frac{(c - m)\sqrt{2mc - m^2}}{2}$$

if and only if both m and c satisfy definition (1).

Proof. Let area of the right triangle be

$$\frac{\text{base}(b) \times \text{height}(h)}{2} \quad \text{as in [1].} \quad (11)$$

Then we substitute equation (1) and (8) into equation (11)

which gives

$$A = \frac{(c-m)\sqrt{2mc-m^2}}{2}$$

which completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3.8 *If θ satisfies definition (2) then area (A) of the right triangle is*

$$\frac{0.5m^2 \text{Sin}\theta \text{Cos}\theta}{\text{Cos}^2\theta - 2\text{Cos}\theta + 1}$$

if and only if m satisfies definition (1).

Proof. Let area = $\frac{\text{base} \times \text{height}}{2}$ as in [1] (12)

But

$$b = \frac{m \text{Cos}\theta}{1 - \text{Cos}\theta} \quad (\text{see equation 3})$$

and

$$(h) = \frac{m \text{Sin}\theta}{1 - \text{Cos}\theta} \quad (\text{see equation 10})$$

Then equation (12) become

$$\frac{\left(\frac{m \text{Cos}\theta}{1 - \text{Cos}\theta}\right) \times \left(\frac{m \text{Sin}\theta}{1 - \text{Cos}\theta}\right)}{2}$$

then we obtain that

$$A = \frac{0.5m^2 \text{Sin}\theta \text{Cos}\theta}{\text{Cos}^2\theta - 2\text{Cos}\theta + 1}$$

which completes the proof. \square

Theorem 3.9 *If P is the Perimeter of the right triangle, then*

$$P = (2c - m) + \sqrt{(2mc - m^2)}$$

if and only if both c and m satisfy definition(1)

Proof. Let perimeter (P) of the right triangle be $a + b + c$ as in [1]. (13)

Then let

$$h = \sqrt{2mc - m^2} \quad (\text{see equation 8})$$

and

$$b = c - m \quad (\text{see equation 1})$$

We substitute both equations (1 and 8) into equation (13).

Thus we obtain that

$$P = \sqrt{2mc - m^2} + (c - m) + c$$

$$P = (2c - m) + \sqrt{2mc - m^2}$$

which completes the proof. □

Theorem 4.0 *If P is the Perimeter of the right triangle and m satisfies definition (1) then*

$$P = \frac{m(\sin\theta + \cos\theta + 1)}{1 - \cos\theta}$$

if and only if θ satisfies definition (2).

Proof. Let the perimeter of the right triangle be $h + b + c$ as in [1] (14)

But

$$h = \frac{m\sin\theta}{1 - \cos\theta} \quad (\text{see equation 10})$$

$$b = \frac{m\cos\theta}{1 - \cos\theta} \quad (\text{see equation 3})$$

and

$$c = \frac{m}{1 - \cos\theta} \quad (\text{see equation 6})$$

Then we obtain that

$$P = \left(\frac{m\cos\theta}{1 - \cos\theta} + \frac{m\cos\theta}{1 - \cos\theta} + \frac{m}{1 - \cos\theta} \right)$$

$$P = \frac{m(\sin\theta + \cos\theta + 1)}{1 - \cos\theta}$$

$$P = \frac{m(\sin\theta + \cos\theta + 1)}{1 - \cos\theta}$$

which completes the proof of Theorem 4.0, further examples are shown in **table 1**. □

Table1. First seven Mambosasa triangle orders within a minimum angle of 36.87°.

Mambosasa Triangle order(<i>m</i>)	Minimum angle(<i>θ</i>)	Height(<i>h</i>) in centimetre	Hypotenuse(<i>c</i>) in centimetre	Base(<i>b</i>) in centimetre
1	36.87°	2.99999	4.99997	3.99997
2	36.87°	5.99998	9.999946	7.999946

3	36.87°	8.99997	14.99991	11.99991
4	36.87°	11.99996	19.99988	15.99988
5	36.87°	14.99995	24.99985	19.99985
6	36.87°	17.99994	29.99982	23.99982
7	36.87°	20.99993	34.99979	27.99979

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